

Face Detection System with Face Recognition

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ABSTRACT

The face is one of the easiest ways to distinguish the individual identity of each other. Face recognition is a personal identification system that uses personal characteristics of a person to identify the person's identity. Human face recognition procedure basically consists of two phases, namely face detection, where this process takes place very rapidly in humans, except under conditions where the object is located at a short distance away, the next is the introduction, which recognizes a face as individuals. Stage is then replicated and developed as a model for facial image recognition (face recognition) is one of the much-studied biometrics technology and developed by experts. There are two kinds of methods that are currently popular in developed face recognition patterns, namely, the Eigenface method and Fisherface method. Facial image recognition Eigenface method is based on the reduction of face dimensional space using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for facial features. The main purpose of the use of PCA on face recognition using Eigenfaces was formed (face space) by finding the eigenvector corresponding to the largest eigenvalue of the face image. The area of this project's face detection system with face recognition is Image processing. The software requirements for this project is matlab software.

Index Terms- Face Detection, Eigen Face, Pca, Matlab

1. INTRODUCTION

Face recognition is the task of identifying an already detected object as a known or unknown face. Often the problem of face recognition is confused with the problem of face detection. Face Recognition on the other hand is to decide if the "face" is someone known, or unknown, using for this purpose a database of faces in order to validate this input face.

There are two predominant approaches to the face recognition problem: Geometric (feature based) and photometric (view based). As researcher interest in face recognition continued, many different algorithms were developed, three of which have been well studied in face recognition literature.

Recognition algorithms can be divided into two main approaches:

Geometric: Is based on geometrical relationship between facial landmarks, or in other words the spatial configuration of facial features. That means that the main geometrical features of the face such as the eyes, nose and mouth are first located and then faces are classified on the basis of various geometrical distances and angles between features.

- Photometric stereo: Used to recover the shape of an object from a number of images taken under different lighting conditions. The shape of the recovered object is defined by a gradient map, which is made up of an array of surface normals (Zhao and Chellappa, 2006).

Popular recognition algorithms include:

- Principal Component Analysis using Eigen faces (PCA)
- Linear Discriminant Analysis,
- Elastic Bunch Graph Matching using the Fisher face algorithm.

1.1 Face Detection

Face detection involves separating image windows into two classes; one containing faces (turning the background (clutter)). It is difficult because although commonalities exist between faces, they can vary considerably in terms of age, skin color and facial expression. The problem is further complicated by differing lighting conditions, image qualities and geometries, as well as the possibility of partial occlusion and disguise. An ideal face detector would therefore be able to detect the presence of any face under any set of lighting conditions, upon any background. The face detection task can be broken down into two steps. The first step is a classification task that takes some arbitrary image as input and outputs a binary value of yes or no, indicating whether there are any faces present in the

image. The second step is the face localization task that aims to take an image as input and output the location of any face or faces within that image as some bounding box with (x, y, width, height).

The face detection system can be divided into the following steps: -

Pre-Processing: To reduce the variability in the faces, the images are processed before they are fed into the network. All positive examples that is the face images are obtained by cropping images with frontal faces to include only the front view. All the cropped images are then corrected for lighting through standard algorithms.

- **Classification:** Neural networks are implemented to classify the images as faces or non faced by training on these examples. We use both our implementation of the neural network and the Matlab neural network toolbox for this task. Different network configurations are experimented with to optimize the results.
- **Localization:** The trained neural network is then used to search for faces in an image and if present localize them in a bounding box. Various Feature of Face on which the work has been done on:- Position Scale Orientation Illumination.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Face detection is a computer technology that determines the location and size of a human face in an arbitrary (digital) image. The facial features are detected and any other objects like trees, buildings and bodies etc are ignored from the digital image. It can be regarded as a 'specific' case of object-class detection, where the task is finding the location and sizes of all objects in an image that belong to a given class. Face detection, can be regarded as a more 'general' case of face localization. In face localization, the task is to find the locations and sizes of a known number of faces (usually one). Basically there are two types of approaches to detect facial parts in the given image i.e. feature base and image base approach. Feature based approach tries to extract features of the image and match it against the knowledge of the face features. The image base approach tries to get the best match between training and testing images.

Fig 2.1 detection methods

3. FEATURE BASED APPROACH

Active Shape Model Active shape models focus on complex non-rigid features like actual physical and higher-level appearance of features Means that Active Shape Models (ASMs) are aimed at automatically locating landmark points that define the shape of any statistically modeled object in an image. When facial features such as the eyes, lips, nose, mouth and eyebrows. The training stage of an ASM involves the building of a statistical

- facial model from a training set containing images with manually annotated landmarks. ASMs is classified into three groups i.e. snakes, PDM, Deformable templates
- Snakes:** The first type uses a generic active contour called snakes, first introduced by Kass et al. in 1987 Snakes are used to identify head boundaries [8,9,10,11,12]. In order to achieve the task, a snake is first initialized at the proximity around a head boundary. It then locks onto nearby edges and subsequently assumes the shape of the head. The evolution of a snake is achieved by minimizing an energy function, Esnake (analogy with physical systems), denoted as $Snake = Internal + EExternal$ Where internal and EExternal are internal and external energy functions. Internal energy is the part that depends on the intrinsic properties of the snake and defines its natural evolution. The typical natural evolution in snakes is shrinking or expanding. The external energy counteracts the internal energy and enables the contours to deviate from the natural evolution and eventually assume the shape of nearby features—the head boundary at a state of equilibria. Two main considerations for forming snakes i.e.

selection of energy terms and energy minimization. Elastic energy is used commonly as internal energy. Internal energy varies with the distance between control points on the snake, through which we get contour, an elastic-band characteristic that causes it to shrink or expand. On the other side external energy relies on image features. Energy minimization process is done by optimization techniques such as the steepest gradient descent. Which needs the highest computations. Huang and Chen and Lam and Yan both employ fast iteration methods by greedy algorithms. Snakes have some demerits like contour often becomes trapped onto false image features and another one is that snakes are not suitable in extracting non convex features.

3.1 Deformable Templates

Deformable templates were then introduced by Yuille et al. to take into account the a priori of facial features and to better the performance of snakes. Locating a facial feature boundary is not an easy task because the local evidence of facial edges is difficult to organize into a sensible global entity using generic contours. The low brightness contrast around some of these features also makes the edge detection process. Yuille et al. took the concept of snakes a step further by incorporating global information of the eye to improve the reliability of the extraction process.

Deformable template approaches are developed to solve this problem. Deformation is based on local valley, edge, peak, and brightness. Other than face boundary, salient feature (eyes, nose, mouth and eyebrows) extraction is a great challenge of face recognition.

$$E = E_v + E_e + E_p + E_i + E_{\text{internal}} ;$$

where E_v , E_e , E_p , E_i , Internal are external energy due to valley, edges, peak and image brightness and internal energy.

3.2 PDM (Point Distribution Model):

Independently of computerized image analysis, and before ASMs were developed, researchers developed statistical models of shape. The idea is that once you represent shapes as vectors, you can apply standard statistical methods to them just like any other multivariate object. These models learn allowable constellations of shape points from training examples and use principal components to build what is called a Point Distribution Model. These have been used in diverse ways, for example for categorizing Iron Age brooches. Ideal Point Distribution Models can only deform in ways that are characteristic of the object. Coots and his colleagues were seeking models which do exactly that so if a beard, say, covers the chin, the shape model can "override the image" to approximate the position of the chin under the beard. It was therefore natural (but perhaps only in retrospect) to adopt Point Distribution Models. This synthesis of ideas from image processing and statistical shape modelling led to the Active Shape Model. The first parametric statistical shape model for image analysis based on principal components of inter-landmark distances was presented by Cootes and Taylor in. On this approach, Cootes, Taylor, and their colleagues, then released a series of papers that culminated in what we call the classical Active Shape Model.

3.3 Low Level Analysis

Based on low level visual features like color, intensity, edges, motion etc. Skin Color Base Color is a vital feature of human faces. Using skin-color as a feature for tracking a face has several advantages. Color processing is much faster than processing other facial features. Under certain lighting conditions, color is orientation invariant. This property makes motion estimation much easier because only a translation model is needed for motion estimation. Tracking human faces using color as a feature has several problems like the color representation of a face obtained by a camera is influenced by many factors (ambient light, object movement, etc)

Fig 2.2. face detection

Majorly three different face detection algorithms are available based on RGB, YCbCr, and HIS color space models. In the implementation of the algorithms there are three main steps viz.

- Classify the skin region in the color space,
- Apply threshold to mask the skin region and
- Draw a bounding box to extract the face image.

Crowley and Coutaz suggested simplest skin color algorithms for detecting skin pixels. The perceived human color varies as a function of the relative direction to the illumination.

The pixels for skin region can be detected using a normalized color histogram, and can be normalized for changes in intensity on dividing by luminance. Converted an [R, G, B] vector is converted into an [r, g] vector of normalized color which provides a fast means of skin detection. This algorithm fails when there are some more skin region like legs, arms, etc. Cahil and Ngan [27] suggested skin color classification algorithm with YCbCr color space. Research found that pixels belonging to skin region having similar Cb and Cr values. So that the thresholds be chosen as [Cr1, Cr2] and [Cb1, Cb2], a pixel is classified to have skin tone if the values [Cr, Cb] fall within the thresholds. The skin color distribution gives the face portion in the color image. This algorithm is also having the constraint that the image should be having only face as the skin region. Kjeldson and Kender defined a color predicate in HSV color space to separate skin regions from background. Skin color classification in HSI color space is the same as YCbCr color space but here the responsible values are hue (H) and saturation (S). Similar to above the threshold be chosen as [H1, S1] and [H2, S2], and a pixel is classified to have skin tone if the values [H,S] fall within the threshold and this distribution gives the localized face image. Similar to the above two algorithms this algorithm is also having the same constraint.

4. CONCLUSION

The computational models, which were implemented in this project, were chosen after extensive research, and the successful testing results confirm that the choices made by the researcher were reliable. The system with manual face detection and automatic face recognition did not have a recognition accuracy over 90%, due to the limited number of eigen faces that were used for the PCA transform. This system was tested under very robust conditions in this experimental study and it is envisaged that real-world performance will be far more accurate. The fully automated frontal view face detection system displayed virtually perfect accuracy and in the researcher's opinion further work need not be conducted in this area.

The only reason for this was the face recognition subsystem did not display even a slight degree of invariance to scale, rotation or shift errors of the segmented face image. This was one of the system requirements identified in section 2.3. However, if some sort of further processing, such as an eye detection technique, was implemented to further normalise the segmented face image, performance will increase to levels comparable to the manual face detection and recognition system. Implementing an eye detection technique would be a minor extension to the implemented system and would not require a great deal of additional research. All other implemented systems displayed commendable results and reflect well on the deformable template and Principal Component Analysis strategies. The most suitable real-world applications for face detection and recognition systems are for mugshot matching and surveillance. There are better techniques such as iris or retina recognition and face recognition using the thermal spectrum for user access and user verification applications since these need a very high degree of accuracy. The real-time automated pose invariant face detection and recognition system proposed in chapter seven would be ideal for crowd surveillance applications. If such a system were widely implemented its potential for locating and tracking suspects for law enforcement agencies is.

The implemented fully automated face detection and recognition system (with an eye detection system) could be used for simple surveillance applications such as ATM user security, while the implemented manual face detection and automated recognition system is ideal for mugshot matching. Since controlled conditions are present when mugshots are gathered, the frontal view face recognition scheme should display a recognition accuracy far better than the results, which were obtained in this study, which was conducted under adverse conditions.

Furthermore, many of the test subjects did not present an expressionless, frontal view to the system. They would probably be more compliant when a 6'5" policeman is taking their mugshot! In mugshot matching applications, perfect recognition accuracy or an exact match is not a requirement. If a face recognition system can reduce the number of images that a human operator has to search through for a match from 10000 to even a 100, it would be of incredible practical use in law enforcement. The automated vision systems implemented in this thesis did not even approach the performance, nor were they as robust as a human's innate face recognition system. However, they give an insight into what the future may hold in computer vision.

5. REFERENCES

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